

From online training on Open Science to the design and delivery of Open Educational Resources

*An example of FAIR-ification of
digital training resources*

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Conferenza GARR 2022
Palermo 18-20 maggio

Triple

Transforming Research Through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

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TRIPLE Open Science Training Series

TRIPLE Open Science Training Series

**The Importance of
User-Centred Design for Open Science**

>> Webinar on 16 February 2022, 14:00 – 15:30 (CET) <<

TRIPLE Open Science Training Series

**Multilingual Vocabularies for the Social
Sciences and Humanities**

ALT >> Webinar on 20th April 2022, 14:00 – 15:30 (CET) <<

- Need for **increased skills in Open Science practices** and workflows
- Need to build a **shared understanding** of the **latest European Open Science advancements**
- Need to establish **common practices** in managing FAIR training materials

<https://project.gotriple.eu/training/>

Activities & Results

Online training

Guidelines and training material

Collaboration with research infrastructures and training communities

11 training sessions since June 2021

550 researchers trained

715 Downloads on Zenodo

367 Views on Youtube

4

Guidelines to produce FAIR materials

TRIPLE **Training Toolkit**

Training resources hosted on DARIAH Campus

 <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjwEHdltYYhocCC9o6RljuQ/>
featured

 <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/?page=1&size=20>

 <https://campus.dariah.eu/source/triple/page/1>

Challenges in achieving FAIR-by-design: The example of the TRIPLE Open Science Training Series

February 25, 2022

TRIPLE Training Toolkit

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The TRIPLE Training Toolkit is part of the work performed by Work Package 6 (WP6) under Task 6.3 in the TRIPLE Project (Transforming Research through Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration). The project is funded by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement No. 863420 and will run for 42 months starting from October 2019.

The TRIPLE Open Science Training Series focuses on the design and delivery of competence-oriented training to address the specific and general needs of the research community on Open Science topics and on the EOSC.

The experiment enabled a reflection on the current challenges to make FAIR-by-design training resources and how to overcome them.

The following files are deposited in Zenodo to serve as a reference for those wishing to reproduce this experiment within their own institution or for their own training activities.

Please note that the training series are still ongoing and as such the present document and the files listed below will be followed by updated versions by the end of the project (2023).

The first document to read is the README.

Name	Size	Download
01 README.docx	8.2 kB	Download
02 Guidelines_Organisation_TRIPLE_Training_Toolkit.docx	19.6 kB	Download
03 To_Do_TRIPLE_Training_Toolkit.xlsx	18.8 kB	Download
04 List_Past_Events_TRIPLE_Training_Toolkit.docx	11.0 kB	Download
05 Training_Objectives_Learning_Outcomes_TRIPLE_Training_Toolkit.docx	225.6 kB	Download
06 Internal_Training_Needs_Survey_TRIPLE_Training_Toolkit.docx	8.2 kB	Download

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Communities

OPERAS: open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities

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- 10.5281/zenodo.6207720 (Lesson)
- 10.5281/zenodo.5795376 (Lesson)
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- 10.5281/zenodo.5510388 (Lesson)
- 10.5281/zenodo.5045044 (Lesson)

<https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007854>

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Challenges in achieving FAIR-by-design: The example of the TRIPLE Open Science Training Series

Guidelines for the organisation of TRIPLE Open Science training events

Contents

Guidelines for organisers

Before the event

After the event

Instructions for moderators

Before the event

After the event

Instructions for speakers/presenters

Before the event

After the event

2
2
4
4
4
4
4
4

3 To_Do_TRIPLE_Training_Toolkit							
INSERT DATE AND TITLE OF THE EVENT		For details see Guidelines					
Task	Deadline	Resp. person	Status	Links/references	Involved team		
Create zoom link				Add zoom link			
Provide short description of the event to WP6				Add link to the registration form			
Duplicate template documents							
Send template slides to speaker							
Upload description of the event on website (include registration link)							
Create Email for partners to register (include registration link)							
Create Invitation campaign on Mailchimp (include registration link)							
Create Reminder campaign (x2) on Mailchimp							
Create a Tag with the name of the event on Mailchimp							
Create Mentimeter survey							
Send Email to partners to register	2 weeks before the event						
Send Invitation campaign to potential participants via Mailchimp (send to the entire audience, include registration link)	2 weeks before the event						
Disseminate event on social media							
Share the questions collected from the partners to the speaker (if any)							
Import small addresses from the registration form in Mailchimp, tag them with name of the event.							
Send Reminder campaign #1 via Mailchimp (use the tag of the event)	2 days before the event			on the day of the event			
Final import of registered small addresses in Mailchimp, tag them with name of the event	on the day of the event			on the day of the event			
Send Reminder campaign #2 via Mailchimp (use the tag of the event)	on the day of the event			on the day of the event			
Update Mentimeter code on the speaker slides	on the day of the event			on the day of the event			
Start the session recording	on the day of the event			on the day of the event			
Important: make sure no one will use the zoom account at the same time							
Show the survey on mentimeter at the end of the session							
Keep track of number of attendees after the event							
Send speaker slides to WP8 leader (or WP6) to be stored on Zenodo, Nakala and Youtube							
Send video recording to WP8 leader (or WP6) to be stored on Zenodo, Nakala and Youtube							
Deposit your presentation (slides) in the dedicated folder in G-drive				Add link to the Google Drive folder			
Store slides on Zenodo following the procedure designed by WP8							
Download the data from the post-training survey on Mentimeter and and insert the data in the dedicated spreadsheet				Add link to a common spreadsheet which gathers all the data from past surveys			

5 Training_Objectives_Learning_Outcomes_TRIPLE_Training_Toolkit	
6 EOSC Architecture	
Training objectives	Provide an overview of the EOSC Architecture principles, the EOSC Future guiding principles and the Minimum Viable EOSC. Explain the main components of the EOSC Architecture (EOSC Core, EOSC Exchange, EOSC Support Activities and the EOSC Interoperability Framework). Present the scope and purpose of the EOSC Interoperability Framework and its importance in federating the services that will compose the EOSC. Provide information on challenges to achieving technical, semantic, organisational and legal interoperability and a set of recommendations.
Learning outcomes	State the principles of the EOSC Architecture. Describe the main components of the EOSC Architecture. Analyse interoperability issues in the EOSC Architecture. Name the projects and further developments of the EOSC Architecture.
7 Visual Data Discovery for the Social Sciences and Humanities Context	
Training objectives	Present discovery challenges in the SSH. Explain the different applications knowledge maps and stream graphs can have. Present the discovery features of the GoTriple platform.
Learning outcomes	State how knowledge maps and <u>streamgraphs</u> can help researchers overcome discovery challenges. Visually explore research topics and recognize trends in research with GoTriple. Produce and interpret knowledge maps and <u>streamgraphs</u> on the GoTriple platform.

Thank you !

For more information

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